

Spatial Information as a Source to Assess the Suitability of Sponge City Elements in Arid Regions

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Abstract. The poster introduces some basic considerations, goals and approaches envisaged in a pre-project (“RAIN-GIS”) that is currently carried out in a universities’ cooperation between Germany and Jordan. As one opportunity to mitigate negative consequences of drought, the sponge city concept is discussed. Within the RAIN-GIS-project, these considerations are currently elaborated aiming at setting up a scientifically sound framework in which sponge city elements can be conceptualized, tested, and finally evaluated, based on the analysis of spatial data, as well as demographic and socio-economic information.

Keywords. Climate change adaptation, Sponge City, Arid Regions, GIS

1 Introduction

Water shortage is a problem facing over eighty countries, where about 2 billion people lack access to clean water. This issue affects health, well-being, and overall quality of life. For instance, Jordan is one of the four most water-scarce countries in the world, with less than 150 m³ of water available per capita per year (MWI 2015, 2021). This is estimated to drop to about 91 m³ per capita per year by 2025 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Climate zones of Jordan (Source: present and future Köppen-Geiger climate classification maps. Nature Scientific Data) (Albaidaneh 2023)

The increasing need for potable water due to urbanization and population increase demands the development of non-traditional water resources for domestic uses (Assayed et al. 2013). The Urban Heat Island (UHI) is induced by a combination of factors, among others street canyon geometry, the amount of artificial surfaces with increased emissivity, lacking greenery, and anthropogenic heat production. Even this phenomenon is well-known, it arises nowadays as a problem field that suffers from increasing temperatures, combined with heavy rainfall on the one, and long periods of drought on the other hand (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Reasons, effects and solutions concerning the UHI (Godse 2025)

2 RAIN-GIS-project

One goal of the RAIN-GIS project is to assess the above-mentioned elements concerning their potential to support water storage and adaptation to high temperatures. This requires integrating local stakeholders, their expertise and data. On such a fundament, new concepts to improve water storage and to combat the negative effects of UHI can be developed. Sponge city elements, for instance, sidewalks, parks, green roofs, urban wetlands, green belts, water-resilient roads, catchment wells, are designed to absorb storm water and floodwaters, allowing the water to filter through the soil and gradually be released (Ayad et. al 2022).

During the discussions between German and Jordanian partners it was clarified that the goals concern not only technical questions, but that the subject includes societal and political dimensions. Decision-making processes should rely on scientifically sound groundings. The RAIN-GIS results are expected to support these processes using spatial data analysis and visualization (e. g. 2D maps, 3D-city models; satellite image analysis). An important aspect is also that not only the geographic conditions, but especially the decision-making processes are completely different in Europe and the Middle East (OECD 2023; Al-Houri and Al-Omari

2022; Saidan et al 2015). GIS-based analyses must therefore be related to socio-economic and cultural frameworks (Pundt et al 2024). The project will be grounded on a transdisciplinary approach aiming at relating scientific results and stakeholder perspectives (Heilmann and Pundt 2021). Using IPCC climate scenarios will help to evaluate potentially worsening conditions in future (IPCC 2014).

3 Outlook

Within the framework of the evaluation of the suitability of sponge city elements in arid, urban environments, spatial data will play a crucial role. Climate data, land cover, land use, water resources, city infrastructures and new urban development areas, growing rapidly in the suburbs of cities in Jordan, will be analysed using GIS. The main next step is to work out a comprehensive application that enables the scientists from Germany and Jordan to proceed with their ideas and goals.

Data and Software Availability

Due to its character as a pre-project, decisions on datasets and software haven't be made yet. Currently,

only test datasets have been used. Only open and self-developed software tools were and will be used.

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